

Simurgh Soccer 2D Simulation Team Description Paper 2024

Ali Maalekpour², Marziyeh Karimzadeh¹, Ali Poorhoseini, Amirhossein Vahedi
Gharabaei, and Venous Kord

¹ Dept. of Mathematics, Statistics and Computer Science, Isfahan University, Iran

² Ali.maalekpour@gmail.com

Abstract. The Simurgh team is participating in the competition for the first time, and its ultimate goal is the development of artificial intelligence and machine learning in all aspects of the game. In this endeavor, the team aims to implement a set of simple decision-making algorithms to enhance passing and shooting performance. The base code used by Simurgh is Helios base.

Keywords: RoboCup · 2D Soccer Simulation · Artificial Intelligence
· Machine Learning.

1 Introduction

RoboCup, established in 1996 by a consortium of university professors, is an annual international robotics tournament. Its primary objective is to foster advancements in robotics and AI research through the provision of a captivating challenge[8].

The International IranOpen RoboCup competitions have been held annually since 2006 with the support of the RoboCup Federation and are organized by the Iranian RoboCup National Committee. The 2D Soccer Simulation League is the oldest and one of the most active in soccer simulation leagues, which began in 1997 as part of the RoboCup competitions[9].

As the name implies, the 2D Soccer Simulation is a soccer simulation that is limited to two dimensions (x and y) and simulates the actions of a real soccer game. In RoboCup competitions, this simulation environment is used as one of the competitive platforms. Each team in this space consists of 11 players and one coach. Individual players are connected to the main game server and send commands to it. Players can only communicate with each other through pointing (Point To) and speech (Say and Hear). The game progresses at 6,000 cycles in standard mode. Players and coaches must send their commands within the time frame between two cycles.

Each player's vision in this environment is independent, limited, and noisy, but the coach's vision is unlimited and without noise.

Just like real soccer players, players in this game are capable of tackling, moving in any direction, shooting at any angle, and even getting tired and receiving

yellow or red cards[1, 10].

The Simurgh team, which is taking part in this exhilarating competition for the first time, intends to develop artificial intelligence in all aspects of the game. Specifically, in this competition, Helios base has been used[4], and Simurgh aims to implement simple intelligent algorithms for passing and shooting.

2 Related Works

Here, We will explore papers published by 2D teams.

- Alice team has focused on refining the decision tree for Monte Carlo algorithms and combined strategy modifications for on-court player types to improve passing and shooting performance[7].
- HELIOS team’s strategies for improving passing and shooting performance involve dynamically adjusting player positions during a game to create more favorable matchups based on the abilities of their players and their opponents[6].
- CYRUS team’s focus is on using advanced techniques such as neural networks to enhance passing and shooting performance[3].
- The 8 team has applied a fuzzy algorithm for making pass decisions, which considers the position of the ball and the player’s situation to determine the most suitable pass type. Furthermore, they have employed the Multi-Group Ant Colony Optimization (MACO) algorithm for offensive tactics. This algorithm entails training the preference values of actions in different environments and choosing the optimal attacking action based on these preferences. These strategies have played a significant role in enhancing the team’s passing and shooting performance[2].
- ARAS team has devised two strategies aimed at enhancing passing and shooting performance:
 - Offensive Positioning through Pass Simulation: The team conducted simulations for passes across various player positions. They analyzed potential pass receptions within their formation to identify optimal areas for receiving productive passes. Additionally, they accounted for potential secondary passes from teammates. This approach ensured that non-kickable players were strategically positioned to receive the ball promptly.
 - Offensive Decision Making using Markov Decision Process (MDP): Leveraging MDP, the team made offensive decisions considering the stochastic nature of the 2D Soccer Simulation environment. Given the environment’s unpredictability, each action yields different potential outcomes. By simulating scenarios involving noise, they calculated success probabilities for each action (pass, dribble, or shoot). This method enabled the team to make more informed and less risky decisions[5].

3 Offense

3.1 Pass Decision-Making

We have implemented a simple intelligent algorithm for decision-making (using if-else statements), where the player decides which teammate -based on its field of view- should be the target for a pass.

In summary, our algorithm is as follows:

- Inputs:
 - Distance to Teammates: This input is crucial for calculating the required pass power and trajectory to reach each teammate accurately.
 - Player's Position on the Field: Knowing the player's role (defender, midfielder, forward) is important for deciding the best passing option based on the game situation and tactics.
 - Opponent's Defensive Situation: Understanding the positions and number of opposing defenders is essential for finding the best passing lane and avoiding interceptions.
- Algorithm:

This algorithm follows a rule-based approach using if-else statements. First, the player's position and the opponent's defensive situation are evaluated. Then, the distances to all visible teammates are calculated. Based on these inputs, the best passing option is selected according to the following rules:

 1. If the player is in an attacking position (forward) and the opponent's defensive line is broken, the nearest open teammate in an attacking position is chosen as the pass target.
 2. If the player is in a midfield position and the opponent's defensive line is compact, a teammate in a midfield position with more space is preferred as the pass target.
 3. If the player is in a defensive position, priority is given to passing to teammates who are in a better position to advance the ball or maintain possession safely.
 4. If multiple teammates satisfy the above conditions, the one with the shortest passing distance is chosen.
 5. If no suitable passing option is found, the algorithm may decide to dribble, clear the ball, or pass back, depending on the specific situation and priorities set.

This algorithm aims to make informed passing decisions by considering the player's role, game situation, defensive pressure, and available passing options. It prioritizes passing to open teammates in advantageous positions while accounting for defensive coverage and passing distance.

3.2 Shoot Decision-Making

We have developed a simple intelligent algorithm for decision-making (using if-else statements) on whether to shoot or not during gameplay. The decision is based on two main inputs:

- Player’s Distance to the Goal: This input is chosen because it directly affects the probability of scoring. The closer the player is to the goal, the higher the chances of scoring, assuming no other obstacles or defenders in the way.
- Player’s Distance to the Opponent’s Defensive Wall: This input is chosen because it represents the defensive pressure from the opposing team. If the player is too close to the defensive wall, the chances of a successful shoot are lower due to the increased likelihood of the shoot being blocked or deflected.

Our algorithm uses these two inputs to determine the favorability of taking a shoot, following the steps below:

1. Set two distance thresholds: a goal distance threshold and a defensive wall distance threshold. These thresholds should be chosen based on the dimensions of the field and the desired shooting conditions.
 - For the goal distance threshold, we take into account the maximum length of the field along the X-axis, which is from -52.5 to 52.5 in this case. Considering that a shoot taken from a distance too far from the goal has a low probability of scoring, we set the goal distance threshold to a value that represents a reasonable shooting range. In this case, we have set the goal distance threshold to 30.0, which means that if the player is within a distance of 30 units from the opponent’s goal, they are considered to be in a favorable shooting range.
 - For the defensive wall distance threshold, we assume that the opponent’s defensive wall is positioned parallel to the goal line and is located at a distance equal to the length of the penalty area from the goal. Based on this assumption, we set the defensive wall distance threshold to 20.0, which means that if the player is at least 20 units away from the defensive wall, they are considered to be sufficiently far from the defensive pressure, making it a favorable situation for attempting a shoot.
2. Calculate the player’s distance to the opponent’s goal.
3. Calculate the player’s distance to the opponent’s defensive wall.
4. If the player’s distance to the goal is less than the goal distance threshold, it means the player is within a favorable shooting range. In this case:
 - If the player’s distance to the defensive wall is greater than the defensive wall distance threshold, it indicates that the player is sufficiently far from the defensive wall, and the algorithm suggests taking a shoot.
 - Otherwise, if the player is too close to the defensive wall, the algorithm advises against taking a shoot, as it would be a risky situation.
5. If the player’s distance to the goal is greater than the goal distance threshold, it means the player is too far from the goal, resulting in a low scoring probability. In this case, the algorithm suggests not taking a shoot.

The primary aim of this algorithm is to enhance players’ decision-making process during the game, particularly in situations where they must choose whether to attempt a shoot based on their position relative to the goal and the defensive arrangement of the opponent. By considering these two crucial factors, the algorithm provides a simple yet effective guideline for making informed shooting decisions.

4 Future Ideas

Using reinforcement learning in 2D soccer simulation games can be a powerful tool for improving team and player performance in various game scenarios[3]. This can particularly be impactful through learning from mistakes and engaging in multi-agent learning.

We intend to implement these strategies in the future:

- Learning from Mistakes: In reinforcement learning, players and teams can learn from their past mistakes and make better decisions in the future. For example, if a player made a wrong decision in a specific situation in the past resulting in the opponent scoring a goal, they can learn from that experience and make better decisions in similar situations in the future.
- Multi-Agent Learning: In multi-agent learning, each player or agent interacts simultaneously with other agents in the environment and learns from their experiences. This type of learning allows players to learn from the behaviors and decisions of their teammates and act accordingly.
- Rewards and Penalties: Reinforcement learning enables the application of rewards and penalties based on player performance. These rewards and penalties can help players make better decisions in the game and learn from their past mistakes.

In general, through the use of reinforcement learning and multi-agent learning, significant improvements can be made in the performance of teams and players in 2D soccer simulation games, leveraging past experiences to enhance gameplay.

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